

Bangladesh - China Bilateral Relations: *Current Trend Analysis*

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ABSTRACT: Bangladesh – China relationship has been fantastic by the political, monetary and military ties throughout the most recent few decades. Key relations among Bangladesh and China were set up in 1976, and to be straightforward, various specialists on worldwide relations dissected the method of two-sided relations since the establishment of placating relations 45 years back, and applauded dynamic joint effort and affiliation that have been preceding between the two countries various regions of common interest. They reviewed that the relations between the people of these two nations go back to hundreds of years. However, it is emphasized that the progressive heads of these two nations made significant commitments to the advancement of China-Bangladesh relations. Moreover, it can be mentioned that the solidification and upgradation of China-Bangladesh relation and participation serve the major interests of these two nations, meet the regular goals of the people and help towards building harmony and improvement in the areas of development. Thus it is suggested that a "Closer Complete Organization of Participation" between China and Bangladesh is set up based on the standards of longstanding kinship, uniformity, and shared advantage. With the unique initiative of Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina, the two nations have assented to keep on state visits and contacts between government associations, parliaments, philosophical gatherings, military, and non-authoritative social occasions of the two countries; advance correspondence and coordinated effort at the public authority level. Her administration empowers to redesign the investment instruments, including key gatherings, the Joint Monetary and Exchange Board of trustees and Joint Horticulture Council. Various gatherings have been attempting to heighten support in return, hypothesis, cultivation, transportation and structure improvement dependent on value and basic benefit between the two countries. "Belt and Road Initiative" has been contributory to develop the shared interest of the two nations. "Sister Cities" alliance is the last addition to deepen the mutual interest of both countries. This paper is aimed to investigate current trade, agreements, investment, agriculture, transportation and infrastructural development in the pursuit of bilateral relations between Bangladesh and China. This article has tremendously attempted to disclose the present pattern of two-sided relations between Bangladesh and China under the leadership of Sheikh Hasina in the office of Prime Minister in Bangladesh. Article has been worked out based on literature review and analysis has been made consulting the recent scholarships.

KEYWORDS: Bangladesh, China, Bilateral Relations, Geo-political Interests, Economic Diplomacy, Trade Relations, Citizen Diplomacy, Cultural Exchange

INTRODUCTION

Leadership in international arena means a lot to determine the possible best strategy for maximizing the national interest by the way of rebuilding and deepening bilateral and multilateral relations. Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina has shown excellent leadership and the ability to move the country forward in terms of maintaining Bangladesh's international reputation. Her dynamic leadership has truly influenced the bilateral relations between China and Bangladesh based on mutual trust and mutual interest. The diplomatic relations between Bangladesh and China was established in 1976 with a great commitment in mind to leverage collective efforts of mutual cooperation. Clearly, progressive heads of the two nations made significant commitments to the improvement of China-Bangladesh relations. Union and improvement of China-Bangladesh fellowship and collaboration serve the central interests of both the nations, meet the normal goals of individuals and are helpful for harmony and advancement in the district and the world on the loose. For this reason, why the two sides chose to set up a "Closer Comprehensive Partnership of Cooperation" from the essential viewpoint and based on the standards of longstanding fellowship, equity, and shared advantage. Sharply, the two countries have consented to keep trading undeniable level visits and contacts between the two nations heighten cordial trades between government offices, parliaments, ideological groups, military, and non-legislative gatherings of the two nations. On the other hand, arrangements are made to advance correspondence and collaboration at the neighborhood government level, and upgrade the participation instruments, including conciliatory conferences, the Joint Economic and Trade Committee and Joint Agriculture Committee. They are seriously working from hand to hand in a reacted to comprehension to heighten collaboration in exchange, speculation,

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agribusiness, transportation and framework advancement based on equity and shared advantage (Chowdhury, 2010)& (Islam, 2019). The methodology of the paper is analytical and descriptive in nature. The study has followed qualitative approaches. Secondary data has been collected from different books, journal articles, newspapers, periodicals, research monographs, press release, and electronic sources. The study has also used diplomatic documents made between Bangladesh and China.

BILATERAL RELATIONS: CONCEPTUAL CLARITY

This undertaking takes into account the bilateral relations between two independent countries in the area of trade. For understanding the elements of the exchange relations, recorded relations between two gatherings are likewise singled out for specific thought. Essentially, it is an issue which shows itself in different structures on public, local and global level. It is clear that, realism surfaced as a more grounded, legitimate and intelligent hypothesis in clarifying the world governmental issues just as homegrown legislative issues during fifteenth and sixteenth century. This hypothesis of global governmental issues stayed fruitful in fulfilling the responses to address about circumstances and end results of war. Realism is at times depicted as predominant hypothesis in the field of International Relations. Realism has been implicated in almost every major debate over the last half century. The roots realism can be traced back to antiquity in the famous works from Greece, Rome, India and China. Realist's arguments can be found in Kautilya's Arthshastra who literally tried to clarify the position of potential conquer who always tries to maximize his power (Grieco, 1988). Political authenticity in the twenty century can be dated from 1939 when Edwar Hellet Carr's book *Twenty Years Crisis* overwhelmed different ways of thinking in the field of global relations. They clarified the bizarre idea of world legislative issues and set forward the possibility that there is no amicability of interest among states, each state has diverse public targets and embraces heterogeneous strategies for the achievement of their public objectives. For them it is a senseless desire to accept that the battle for force can be overwhelmed by worldwide ethical quality, global organizations and democratization.

They know about the truth that public interest can't be undermined at any expense. The researchers excused the dreamer approach as a sufficient one to bring harmony and request. These pragmatists legitimize their contention by pointing at the disappointment of League of Nations in neglecting to stop the flare-up of World War - 2 (Weber, 2005). This brought about the breaking of expectations for the individuals who were imagining that optimism can win to reduce war or the conditions that lead to war. The current investigation been planned in the light of authenticity model in order to examine the predominant respective relations among Bangladesh and China to support their public premium.

CHINA-BANGLADESH RELATIONS: HISTORICAL BACKGROUND

The official diplomatic relationship between Bangladesh and China has been developing, with mutual cooperation and friendship five year after the independence of Bangladesh. The Father of the Nation Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was associated with China during his political life and his state philosophy was influenced by the socialism to so extent. In 1952 Bangabandhu travelled to China for attending an international conference. During, the visit, he met Mao Zedong and Zhou Enlai, the legends of the Chinese Revolution (Mujibur Rahman, Sheikh, 2020). During the War of Liberation of Bangladesh in 1971 with Pakistan, Socialist China solidly negated Bangladesh's parcel from Pakistan, in the light of its binds with Pakistan and optional rapprochement with the USA. Beforehand, during and after the clash of opportunity, Bangladesh was viewed as extra space lines up with India and the Soviet Association/USSR by China. At that stage China was affected by two variables, Indo-Soviet Treaty of Peace Friendship and Cooperation and competition among India and China. In 1972, China rehearsed its denial control in the UNO's Security Council to confine Bangladesh's passage into the UNO as a part state. At the post-freedom stage Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman was worried that Bangladesh required China's help to turn into an individual from the UNO. There were likewise financial components which affected him to fabricate cheerful relations with China. Bangladesh Government communicated its eagerness to have great neighborly relations with China. The uplifting disposition with respect to China was obvious in 1974 when there was a deplorable flood in Bangladesh. China transmitted food, covers, and comfortable garments to help the flood casualties. This casual monetary guide and China's green sign to Bangladesh's participation of the UNO show agreeable perspectives towards China-Bangladesh relations (GlobalSecurity.org, Datta, 2008).

In the mid-1970's China and Bangladesh both began participating in respective ties because of a move in the arrangement of the then Bangladeshi President Ziaur Rahman. Starting now and into the foreseeable future both the countries have been proceeding with dynamic cooperation in grouped fields. China followed the strategy of help tact to fortify relations with adjoining nations in South Asia. Particularly Chinese guide contributed towards the creating economy of Bangladesh. During the 1970's China and Bangladesh got occupied with reciprocal ties because of a move in the arrangement of the Bangladeshi President Ziaur Rahman. From that point forward both the nations have occupied with dynamic collaboration in assorted fields, the establishment of which was laid with the consenting to of a two-sided arrangement in 1976. High – level authority trades have empowered the countries to fabricate shared political trust. Deliberately, Bangladesh and China have commonly profited by reciprocal relations.

In the 1980's China followed an international strategy other than help tact. China set up business relations with Bangladesh through exchange participation the regions of safeguard and culture. China made close business, military and social connections with

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Bangladesh and the-then head of Bangladesh Hussain Muhammad Ershad was gotten with much grandeur and warmth following his visit to Beijing in July 1987. In the mid 1980's, both the countries delayed collaboration to the area of instruction, trade and culture. China provided arms to Bangladesh and aided in building arms and ammo plant in Bangladesh. Social participation included zones of writing, training, research, science, innovation, media, the travel industry, sports and so on

In the 1990's Bangladesh got enormous military guide, military preparing, innovation and gear from China. The two nations endorsed from the essential connections to fortify the safeguard collaboration arrangement in 2002 and 2004 individually. 'Bangladesh- China Friendship Year' has proclaimed and celebrated in 2005. However China being the largest trade partner of Bangladesh, an imbalance in the bilateral trade relations in favor of China exists. In 2006-2007, while Bangladesh's imports from China were as high as US \$ 3 billion, its exports to China amounted to just US \$ 200 million. In order to bridge this huge trade gap China has given financial guide to Bangladesh as well as marked the Asia – Pacific Free Trade Agreement (AFTA) to eliminate levy obstructions from wares imported from Bangladesh. Respective exchange added up to US \$ 7 billion of every 2010. Under the Asia – Pacific Trade Agreement (APTA), presently 3095 Bangladeshi items appreciate obligation free admittance to Chinese market which is found incredible. With the new announcement, 97% of Bangladeshi products will join this zero-tariff club from July 1 that raised the numbers of Bangladeshi products with zero duty access to Chinese market to 8256 (The Dhaka Tribune, June 19, 2020) &(The Hindu, June 19,2020).

MAJOR EVIDENCES OF BANGLADESH - CHINA FRIENDSHIP

Bangladesh-China Friendship Bridge was developed and initiated over stream Buriganga interfacing Dhaka-Bikrampur Munshigonj by the Chinese as a badge of this recently progressing political and military relationship. On 4 October 2000, The Ministry of Telecommunication of Bangladesh gave a postal stamp denoting the 25th commemoration of the foundation of Bangladesh-China discretionary relations. At this point, China had given monetary help adding up to US\$300 million to Bangladesh and the respective exchange had arrived at a worth mounting to a billion dollars. In 2002, the Chinese Premier Wen Jiabao made an authority visit to Bangladesh and the two nations pronounced 2005 as the "Bangladesh-China Friendship Year". Based on trust commendable kinship and shared relationship the two nations has marked nine distinctive bi-sidelong arrangements. Indeed, even with the greeting of Bangladesh, China was added as a spectator in the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC). Such energy empowered the two nations to extend bi-horizontal relations to the date.

Without denying the fact, connectivity is crucial for upgrade common regard and shared collaboration between the two nations. In such manner, Bangladesh and China have been arranging a roadway task to interface Chittagong and Kunming through Myanmar. This roadway would give Bangladesh a section into the Mekong sub-district. Chiefly this is a chance to speed up exchange and encourage individuals to-individuals contact inside two countries. Bangladesh's "Look East" approach is basically intended to lessen its reliance on India and open up new ways of collaboration with China and South-East Asia. Notwithstanding, during the time spent guaranteeing this current, Bangladesh's reliance on China has expanded throughout the long term side by side these lines giving China more prominent influence in their two-sided impasses (Uddin and Bhuyian, 2011).

To connect the gigantic exchange hole China has given financial guide to Bangladesh as well as marked the Asia Pacific Free Trade Agreement (AFTA) for eliminating duty boundaries from products imported from Bangladesh. In 2010, two-sided exchange between Bangladesh and China added up to US \$ 7 billion. Remarkably, China has additionally stepped up to the plate and create flammable gas assets and thermal energy stations in Bangladesh. Yunan area of China has looked to take part in financial participation with Bangladesh to amend its own territorial imbalances and access the Bay of Bengal which is landlocked. Bangladesh as well, has offered to set up a Special Economic Zone for China. The 'Concurrence on Economic and Technical Cooperation' and the 'System Agreement' on a concessional credit given by China to Bangladesh are two other critical arrangements endorsed by the two countries. The Chinese People's Association for Friendship with Foreign Countries and the Bangladesh – China People's Friendship Association of Bangladesh coordinated the China-Bangladesh Friendship and Brightness (Ophthalmic) Trip in 2010 to extend their ties (Kabir, 2017).

China made evacuation of levy obstructions to 84 kinds of items imported from Bangladesh under the system of the Asia-Pacific Free Trade Agreement (AFTA). China apparently is warm in decreasing taxes over the exchange of jute and materials (boss homegrown results of Bangladesh). China has additionally offered Bangladesh to build thermal energy stations in Bangladesh to help meet the nation's developing energy needs. Other than this, China made a few recommendations to help the advancement of Bangladesh's petroleum gas assets.

China and Bangladesh, alongside Myanmar, have chosen to construct the 900 km Kunming Highway connecting Chittagong with Kunming through Myanmar to encourage more noteworthy exchange. This would not just conquer the long ocean entry from the east shore of China through Singapore (for trans-shipment) to Bangladesh, however would likewise bring down transport expenses and add to the economy of Yunnan region. This additionally fits well in their joint activity of improving Chittagong port framework that would now be able to be put to double use for trader vessels and furthermore for individuals of the two nations.

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Bangladesh–China–India–Myanmar Forum for Regional Cooperation (BCIM) is a sub-local element of Asian countries focusing on more prominent incorporation of exchange and speculation between the four nations. From the mid-1980s, the Bangladesh Army has been outfitted with Chinese tanks, its naval force has Chinese frigates and rocket boats and the Bangladesh Air Force flies Chinese contender jets. China and Bangladesh marked a "Guard Cooperation Agreement" in 2002 (Keystone Quarterly Review, 2015) and (Haroon, 2005).

China has moreover ventured up and made petrol gas resources and nuclear force plants in Bangladesh. The landlocked Yunan area of China has attempted to partake in monetary cooperation with Bangladesh to address its own common incongruities. Bangladesh also, has offered to set up an Uncommon Monetary Zone for China. The 'Simultaneousness on Financial and Specialized Participation' and the 'Design Understanding' on a concessional advance given by China to Bangladesh are two other tremendous deals set apart by the two nations. The Chinese Individuals' Relationship for Kinship with Outside Nations and the Bangladesh – China Individuals' Kinship Relationship of Bangladesh figured out the China-Bangladesh Fellowship and Splendor (Ophthalmic) Excursion in 2010 to build up their ties. Some place in the scope of 2010 and 2011, 70 awards were given by China to Bangladesh.

CHINA- BANGLADESH RELATIONS UNDER THE LEADERSHIP OF SHEIKH HASINA AS PRIME MINISTER

At the point when Sheikh Hasina turned into the Prime Minister of Bangladesh in 1996, the Government under her initiative followed the strategy of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman in regards to unfamiliar relations. It was "fellowship with all and noxiousness towards none". From the earliest starting point Bangladesh presented its international strategy that was "fellowship to all and noxiousness towards none". 'As needs be the destinations of Bangladesh international strategy were protecting of public sway including regional honesty, the advancement of public financial targets and partnership of public uniqueness. Bangladesh – China strategy was additionally set by these standards (Chakma, 1996). Sheik Hasina was worried about the move in Chinese approach. It is significant that during the virus war period Chinese arrangement was for the most part India-driven on account of India's relations with Soviet Union. After the finish of cold conflict China zeroed in on economy as head denominator. In this specific circumstance while relations with the developing politically influential nation like China were concerned Sheik Hasina chose to make the personality of Bangladesh as organization developer not as a recipient of help. She underlined reciprocal visits for trade of perspectives. In 1996 Agreements were endorsed between these two nations for Inspiring and Protecting Investment, Prevention of Tax Evasion and Avoidance of Double Taxation. Slowly relations between the two nations depended on shared collaboration, trust and kinship. In 1998 China conceded to offer \$24 million interest free credit for the development of Convention Center to hold the NAM Summit Conference in Dhaka in 2001. China likewise offered help for Installation of Digital Telephone Exchange, participation in the water area for flood control and development of the Ganges Barrage (Bhattacharjee, 2019 and The Daily Star, July 8, 2019).

Sheikh Hasina was chosen as Prime Minister of Bangladesh Government in 2008, 2014 and 2019 sequentially for three systems. In 2008 when she came to control for the second time the gathering statement was 'Contract for Change Vision 2021'. 'As to strategy Sheikh Hasina zeroed in addition on financial issues other than political discretion with the goal that the continuous improvement in Bangladesh precedes. China's strategy was to fortify the relations of companionship and collaboration with Bangladesh. Then again Bangladesh considered China as its dear companion and participation accomplice (Kibria, 2011). With Prime Minister (PM) Sheikh Hasina's visit to China from 1 to 5 of July 2019, the relations among China and Bangladesh got an important lift. This was Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina's first visit to China after she framed the public authority for the third back to back term in January 2019. Bangladesh being an essential accomplice of China, PM Hasina's visit pulled in worldwide consideration. China and Bangladesh manufactured an essential organization in 2016. During the visit, PM Sheikh Hasina was energetically gotten by the Chinese initiative as honorary pathway was moved to invite her. Chinese Premier Li Keqiang facilitated a unique supper gathering to pay tribute to PM Hasina. Gatherings were held with President Xi Jinping and the two chiefs examined issues of two-sided significance. The visit was the reassurance of the bonhomie the two nations share. The quick result of the visit was the consenting to of nine two-sided arrangements in the territories including help for the Rohingyas, financial and venture, force, culture, and the travel industry and specialized participation and so on.

The arrangements endorsed between them are: Framework Agreement of Concessional Loan understanding of Expansion of Strengthening Power System Network Under DPDC Area project; Expansion and Strengthening of Power System under Dhaka Power Distribution Company (DPDC) Area project; Framework Agreement of Power Grid Network Strengthening Project; Agreement on Technical and Economic Cooperation; MOU and its execution plan on hydrological data sharing of Yalu Zhangbo/Brahmaputra River; MOU on foundation of venture participation working gathering; MOU on Cultural Exchange and Tourism Program. Plus, the two nations conceded to China giving 2500 tons of rice to the Rohingya exiles in Bangladesh.

A joint statement was issued during the visit that outlined details of the discussion held between the two countries. The areas that gained priority in the discussion were- trade and investment, maritime, defense and security, people-to-people connectivity, climate change, maritime cooperation, climate change, science etc. Significant highlights of the discussion that merits notice are:

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Bangladesh and China consented to hold a discourse on sea undertakings and further investigate available resources to coordinate on Blue Economy, sea the board, marine spatial arranging and joint sea perception among other. Also, the two nations communicated obligation to develop collaboration added to Repertoire Road Initiative (BRI) and work carrying out the Bangladesh, China, India Myanmar (BCIM) Economic hall. BCIM is a quadrilateral activity that interfaces China's Kunming with Kolkata in India by means of Bangladesh and Myanmar. China later announced the activity to be under BRI. In this manner during the second residency Sheik Hasina stressed participation in the regions of political, monetary and military security. China's inclusion was found in the establishment of force age, improvement of infra construction and extensions in Bangladesh. International alliance (FTA) focused on movement of Chinese little and medium undertakings in Bangladesh. Another activity was multilateral commitment among China, India, Myanmar and Bangladesh for cross line infrastructural advancement and improved availability through rail, air, stream and connection streets (UNB, February, 26, 2020, Kabir, 2017).

In the era of globalization and application of neo-liberal economic policies Sheikh Hasina aimed at attracting more investment and boost trade and commercial relations. It is observed that Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Bangladesh has tripled since 2008. It is also observed that both China and Bangladesh enjoy special relationship and reinforce ties bilaterally (Hong, 2009). The nations promised to set up nearer extensive organization of participation from the essential viewpoint and based on the standards of longstanding fellowship, uniformity and common advantage. China has given financial help on simple conditions in building framework like six China-Bangladesh Friendship spans, Barapukuria Plant, one of the four Economic Zones in Bangladesh. Other than in 2010 Sheik Hasina consented to an arrangement with China for foundation of a compost plant, telecom network framework, building Chittagong-Kunming railroad, street correspondence through Myanmar, Bangladesh-China Friendship connect, help with rural area, advancement of sun powered energy. The two nations likewise consented to fabricate participation with Chinese National Hybrid Rice Research Center to create farming in Bangladesh. China consented to give help to water decontamination project, modernizing flood determining and cautioning focus, waterway digging project, satellite dispatching, far off detecting satellite and for expanding grants for Bangladeshi understudies and specialists. (Kabir, 2017)

Bangladesh is the third biggest exchange accomplice of China South Asia. It merits referencing that under the authority of Sheik Hasina Bangladesh has accomplished phenomenal monetary development. A consistent development pace of 7% has driven Bangladesh nearer to the situation with center pay country. China has given enormous exchange support by reporting that 97% of Bangladeshi items will be absolved from tax. At present 3095 Bangladeshi items appreciate obligation free admittance to Chinese market under Asia Pacific Trade Agreement (APTA). Because of the declaration altogether 8256 Bangladeshi items will go under duty exclusion. (Bhattacharjee, 2019)

DIFFERENT DIMENSIONS OF CHINA- BANGLADESH RELATIONS

a) Expansion of Economic Diplomacy (trade and investment)

The Government of Bangladesh drove by Prime Minister Sheik Hasina is attempting to accomplish its higher center pay objective by 2021 and worldwide objectives of Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) by 2030. 'Financial Diplomacy' is focused on by Sheik Hasina. China-Bangladesh relations fall under this strategy system of financial tact. Under the system of the Asia-Pacific Free Trade Agreement (AFTA), China made expulsion of duty boundaries to 84 kinds of items imported from Bangladesh. China is cheerful in lessening taxes over the exchange of jute and materials (boss homegrown results of Bangladesh). China has additionally offered Bangladesh to develop thermal energy stations in Bangladesh to help meet the nation's developing energy needs. Other than this, China made a few proposition to help the advancement of Bangladesh's gaseous petrol assets. China principally imports crude materials from Bangladesh like calfskin, cotton materials, fish, and so on China's significant fares to Bangladesh incorporate materials, hardware and electronic items (Mobile is the main electronic item), concrete, manure, tire, crude silk, maize, and so forth (The Daily Star, 2016).

China has stepped up to the plate and create flammable gas assets and thermal energy stations in Bangladesh. The landlocked Yunan region of China has tried to participate in financial collaboration with Bangladesh to amend its own local imbalances and access the Bay of Bengal. Bangladesh as well, has offered to set up a Special Economic Zone for China. The 'Concurrence on Economic and Technical Cooperation' and the 'System Agreement' on a concessional advance given by China to Bangladesh are two other huge arrangements endorsed by the two countries. (Quy-Toam, 2016)

Other than the oil and gas pipelines, China and Bangladesh, alongside Myanmar, have chosen to construct the 900 km Kunming Highway connecting Chittagong with Kunming through Myanmar to encourage more prominent exchange. This would not just defeat the long ocean section from the east shoreline of China through Singapore (for trans-shipment) to Bangladesh, yet would likewise bring down transport expenses and add to the economy of Yunnan region. This likewise fits well in their joint activity of improving Chittagong port foundation that would now be able to be put to double use for dealer vessels and furthermore for individuals of the two nations (Keystone Quarterly Review, 2015) & (Islam, 2012).

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Moreover, the Bangladesh–China–India–Myanmar Forum for Regional Cooperation (BCIM) is a sub-territorial element of Asian countries focusing on more noteworthy joining of exchange and venture between the four nations. The idea of monetary participation inside the BCIM area was first evolved by Professor Rehman Sobhan who upheld that multi-modular vehicle network, upheld by different activities and framework improvement could altogether lessen exchange costs, animate exchange and venture and therefore speed up development and destitution lightening in this locale. The multi-modular hallway will be the main interstate among India and China and will go through Myanmar and Bangladesh (Keystone Quarterly Review, 2015).

b) Strategic Relations (Defense Cooperation)

From the mid-1980s, the Bangladesh Army has been furnished with Chinese tanks, its naval force has Chinese frigates and rocket boats and the Bangladesh Air Force flies Chinese warrior jets. In 2002, China and Bangladesh marked a "Guard Cooperation Agreement". Under the domain of this agreement, military preparing and guard creation will be covered. As per the report submitted to the United Nations by China in 2006, Dhaka has been significant purchaser of weapons made in China. China sold 65 huge type cannons frameworks, 16 battle airplane and 114 rocket and related hardware to Bangladesh in 2005. Other than this, exactly 200 little arms like guns and sub-automatic weapons have additionally been imported alongside customary 82-mm mortars. In 2008, Bangladesh set up an enemy of boat rocket platform close to the Chittagong Port with help from China (Vijay, 2009, bdnews24.com, 31 Jul 2017).

C) Geo-Political Interest Nexus (Consolidation of Economic Interest)

In the consequence of twentieth century, network has been unique to upgrade shared participation. China and Bangladesh have been arranging a roadway task to interface Chittagong and Kunming through Myanmar. This interstate would give Bangladesh a passage into the Mekong sub-area, which as of now incorporates China, speed up exchange and encourage individuals to-individuals contact. Numerous international strategy specialists of Bangladesh have noticed the degree of discretionary development the Ministry of Foreign Affairs showed with the appropriation of 'Look East Policy' (Kibria, 2006).

Bangladesh's 'Look East' approach is basically intended to bring down its reliance on India and open up new roads of collaboration with China and South-East Asia (Garver, 2010). Executive of Bangladesh received such discretionary viewpoint in accordance with the core value of the constitution of Bangladesh "Kinship towards all, noxiousness toward none" However, during the time spent guaranteeing this current; Bangladesh's reliance on China has expanded throughout the long term, consequently giving China more prominent influence in their two-sided ties. Both the countries have vowed to participate in nearer collaboration, guaranteeing long haul fellowship, uniformity and shared advantage to support their "tried and true all climate kinship" (Mannan, 2018) &(The Daily Star, February 19, 2006).

The geographic territory incorporating South Asia and its touching sea spaces are of developing vital significance to China, as reflected in China's snare of associations and alliances with states in the area (Garver, 2013). The elements of these connections show up on a superficial level to be founded on reliance, yet are really determined by long haul political, financial and key interests. Bangladesh is a significant player out of South Asian states for Beijing's political-military authenticity. Such essential association with Dhaka furnishes China with added influence to check Indian powers. This is apparent from the standard political trades and upgraded military collaboration between the two nations. We can allude to the remarks of Munshi Faiz Ahmad, Bangladesh's representative to China who intentionally said "Bangladesh and China have delighted in a "reliable, all-climate kinship" (The Hindu, 2009).

d) Indian Dilemma on Relationship between Bangladesh and China (Pursuing Balanced Policy)

Bangladesh's relationship with China has tremendously influenced India (Bhaskar, 2019). In 2007, news reports asserted that China was wanting to redirect the water of Brahmaputra waterway to its north-west locales. The Prime Minister of India Manmohan Singh met Chinese president Hu Jintao to plan the principal meeting on this matter. Adding to India's voice was Bangladesh, which would be profoundly influenced if China were to really proceed with its arrangements. It has showed up from various sources that, New Delhi is restless about Bangladesh's developing military contacts on a few fronts (Datta, 2008) & (The Indian Express, October 9, 2019).

India's weakness in the Siliguri passage is the primary concern which frequently alluded to as the 'chicken neck'. This 200 kilometers (km) long and 40 km wide passageway joins territory India by rail, street and air with its Northeast district, a piece of which (90,000 sq. km in Arunachal Pradesh) is guaranteed by China (Sahoo, 2013). Bhutan is its north, and Bangladesh in the south. The Sili guri hall figures unmistakably in the Sino-Bangladesh kinship and the different sides. From the perspective on Indian military specialists, India has nervousness with a conviction that such fellowship triggers a complex system to isolate India from the Northeast area. There are fears that Bangladesh may offer Chittagong port for improvement to China, clearly for business purposes, however which could likewise be utilized for organizing Chinese maritime resources. India additionally has worry on this issue with a confidence that, China will actually want to screen Indian rocket testing directed at Chandipur adrift close, Orissa, Balasore, and furthermore maritime movement in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands in the Bay of Bengal (Kumar, 2010, and Vijay, 2009).

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e) Geo- Economic Policy of “One Belt One Road” (Challenges and Opportunities)

The "One Belt One Road" (OBOR), the brainchild of Chinese President Xi Jinping, is a yearning financial turn of events and business project that centers around improving availability and collaboration among various nations spread across the mainland's of Asia, Africa, and Europe. Named as the "Undertaking of the Century" by the Chinese specialists, OBOR ranges around 78 nations. At first reported in the year 2013 with a reason for reestablishing the antiquated Silk Route that associated Asia and Europe, the task's extension has been extended throughout the years to incorporate new regions and improvement activities. Additionally called the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), the task includes building a major organization of streets, railroads, sea ports, power networks, oil and gas pipelines, and related framework projects. The task is covered by different sides. The first is known as the "Silk Road Economic Belt," which is principally land-based and is required to interface China with Central Asia, Eastern Europe, and Western Europe. The second is known as the "21st Century Maritime Silk Road," which is ocean based and is relied upon to interface China's southern coast to the Mediterranean, Africa, South-East Asia, and Central Asia. The names are befuddling as the 'Belt' is really an organization of streets, and the 'Street' is an ocean course (Benli, 2019).

f) 'Sister urban areas'- Alliance Proposed by The China Communist Party (Citizen Diplomacy)

'The Communist Party of China' (CPC) has offered that China can help Bangladesh in handling the Covid-19 pandemic if the nation consents to frame sister-city partnerships with those Chinese urban areas. The gathering, which has administered China since 1949, additionally communicated its inclination to make the 'Dhaka North City Corporation' (DNCC), just as some other significant city organizations, "sister urban areas" to handle the current Covid-19 pandemic and its difficulties. The CPC proposed to frame sister-city unions with six Bangladeshi urban communities including Dhaka North, one of the two city companies of the capital. The Chinese proposition, considered as an agreeable motion, is generally valued in Bangladesh. All things considered, the Chinese proposal of sister-city coalitions at the hour of Covid-19 pulled in worldwide consideration prompting worries about China's expectation behind the proposition. Authorities of the International Liaison Department of the CPC conferred this data, making the proposition at an online course on countering Covid-19 (ORF, June 12, 2020) & (The Dhaka Tribune May 19, 2020).

Sister urban areas are long haul, expansive based organization between two networks in two nations. After the most noteworthy chosen or named authorities from both the networks consent to an arrangement then the relationship is formally perceived. Sister-urban communities are shaped based on shared arrangements between two urban communities of the two nations to advance and improve the social and business connections. The idea of sister city right off the bat presented by the former US President Dwight D. Eisenhower. The principle driving force behind the sister-city is to elevate individuals to individuals contact or 'resident tact' between the two countries. Customarily, sister-urban areas are considered to have been useful in creating understanding and a feeling of holding among individuals of the two urban communities who confederate. Bangladesh – China kinship turned out to be nearer when the current Government of Bangladesh has shaped since 2008 to work now. The relations between these two nations have made another skyline in the South-East Asian legislative issues as well. The idea of 'sister urban areas' partnership is another element of the political field with regards to South Asia just as South - East Asia (The Dhaka Tribune, May 19, 2020).

APPRAISAL OF SHEIKH HASINA’S DIPLOMACY TOWARDS CHINA: DYNAMIC LEADERSHIP IN PLACE

The two nations have kept their relationship "implied, adaptable and dubious". Such nature of relationship is permitting Dhaka to receive the rewards of an essential organization with an atomic force without including itself in any proper safeguard course of action. Sino-Bangladesh relations are not just a matter of a nearer complete relationship of participation, however a unique cycle which has transformed from the phase of financial organization. Obviously Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina is presently attempting to profit by the international benefit that Bangladesh appreciates as a country which ignores the deliberately significant ocean paths of the Indian Ocean connecting China with the Persian Gulf having a job in getting energy supplies for Beijing. Upon get back from China PM Sheikh Hasina articulated saying that she failed to remember the past in light of a legitimate concern for monetary advantages for her country. Such strategy talks about her vision to pushing forward with the substance of Win-Win circumstance by leaving antagonistic mentality China made during freedom battle in 1971. It is gotten that, Beijing has its own hypothesis of 'pearl necklace', which means bases by which China can enclose India in South Asian legislative issues (Muni, 1991). It has effectively focused on Sri Lanka, Nepal and Bhutan. On the off chance that Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina is presently set up to fail to remember everything before, at that point China would have another vital expansion to its stake. Like other amazing nations in world legislative issues, China has stretched out its vital help to the new government drove by Sheikh Hasina in the repercussions of 5 January political decision in 2014. Chinese Prime Minister Li Keqiang said Beijing might want to hold hands with the Sheikh Hasina-drove government to take "exhaustive and helpful association to another stature" which talks about the developing relations between two countries (Chowdhury, 2016).

The developing reciprocal connections among China and Bangladesh in the previous forty years have to a great extent profited the two countries. Nonetheless, Dhaka-Beijing relations face huge difficulties, especially from a security point of view. China additionally faces rivalry in the Bay of Bengal from certain local and worldwide forces while making key ventures. Geo-political

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factors likewise keep Bangladesh from getting some essential military equipment, including submarines from China. Dhaka's political mechanical assembly has been not exactly effective in managing these issues, ultimately forfeiting public interests.

It is clear that, in light of shared advantage and with common regard, Bangladesh and India are bending over backward towards pushing ahead. The topographical nearness, social partiality and shared history of India and Bangladesh stay as solid base for smoothing out the relationship. Additionally India was the principal nation to perceive Bangladesh as a different and free state and set up discretionary relations with the country following its autonomy in December 1971. India's connections with Bangladesh are civilizational, social, social and financial. There is a lot of that joins the two nations – a common history and basic legacy, etymological and social ties, energy for music, writing and expressions of the human experience. This shared trait is reflected in the multi-dimensional and growing relations. India and Bangladesh's topographical areas supplement one another and present a chance for both to additionally build up their network connections and economies (Rashid, 2010).

In the last over forty years, both the countries have kept on merging their exchange, business, financial, political and social relations and have constructed a thorough institutional system to advance respective participation, what is noticed? Both the nations saw 45 years of respective relations and solid promise from the two sides. Especially Narendra Modi and Sheikh Hasina Government have surrendered further force to the nearby and amicable connection among India and Bangladesh and visit of the Prime Minister of India from 6-7 June 2015 in Dhaka supported speeding up the reciprocal ties between the two nations. Executive Sheikh Hasina and the Government of Bangladesh are saving this energy to proceed for Win-Win factor (Rashid, 2006).

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE AREAS OF COOPERATION

Definitely, China-Bangladesh relations have multi-dimensional underpinnings and importance for Bangladesh's job as a fruitful organization manufacturer. The geographic territory including South Asia and its touching sea spaces are of developing key significance to China, as reflected in China's snare of organizations and alliances with states in the district. The Prime Minister of Bangladesh embraced such discretionary standpoint in accordance with the core value of the constitution of Bangladesh "Companionship towards all, malignance toward none" However, during the time spent guaranteeing this current; Bangladesh's reliance on China has expanded throughout the long term consequently giving China more prominent influence in their reciprocal ties. Both the countries have vowed to take part in nearer collaboration, guaranteeing long haul fellowship, correspondence and shared advantage to support their "reliable all climate kinship". Basically Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina is currently attempting to benefit from the international benefit that Bangladesh appreciates as a country which ignores the deliberately significant ocean paths of the Indian Ocean connecting China with the Persian Gulf having a job in getting energy supplies for Beijing. Such methodology talks about her vision to pushing forward with the embodiment of Win-Win circumstance by leaving threatening demeanor China had during Bangladesh's freedom battle in 1971.

Dhaka has been determined on the alternate path round to build up a sea economy on the planet's biggest cove. To assist the projected endeavor, Dhaka should go on exchange for drawing in with in fact and monetarily widely inclusive accomplices like South Korea, Japan, United States of America and China among others. China in the meantime put \$40 billion in building the "Silk Road" foundation. Provincially, Dhaka needs to have a reasonable connection, especially with New Delhi and Beijing and it is normal that such undertaking will push well forward under the initiative of Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina. All around the world, Bangladesh is additionally bending over backward with the goal that it doesn't confront a circumstance where Dhaka needs to agree with a particular position among Beijing and Washington. China and Bangladesh have same key and business interests on development of a profound water port in Chattagram area. (Bhattacharjee, 2018)

A gathering of investigators accepts that, Bangladesh ought to gain from China for boosting up economy as there are goliath chances for Bangladesh to create and spread with the immediate help of China. Bangladesh can gain from China on how China encourages order, solidarity and ability of improvement. As of late, China reported in the event that they can find antibody on current pandemic which is epidemically bankrupt out everywhere on the globe Covid-19 they will give right off the bat to Bangladesh. Without a doubt this is incredible information for Bangladesh. In current pandemic circumstance the China Communist Party (CPC) proposed Bangladesh to help in handling the Covid-19 pandemic if the nation consents to frame sister-city partnerships with select Chinese urban areas. The Chinese proposition, thought about an amicable motion, is generally valued in Bangladesh. With various political models and training frameworks, Bangladesh won't order comparable approaches of improvement, yet the nation can continue stage by stage as indicated by what turns out best for its economy and society. Bangladesh looks for well-disposed participation to China for a neighborly arrangement of current Rohingya Refugee emergencies. The public authority of Bangladesh needs a significant Rohingya Refugee arrangement under the former Secretary General of UN Kofi Anans ideas which is overall acknowledged equation of repayment of Rohingya Refugee emergencies. Bangladesh accepted that, individuals of Arakan territory of Myanmar are their own status as a person. That is the reason, Bangladesh attempting to bargain this issue with a common regard and participation as well. Bangladesh consistently accept that, in the changing scene you can't do single second without assistance of other country. That is the reason, Bangladesh think about its relations with South Asian and South – East Asian Nations with shared collaboration and trust commendable fellowship with all. Since we follow 'kinship to all and malevolence towards none' this is our

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international strategies primary guideline. Past confirmations show that China – Bangladesh reciprocal relations will spread; the "Thorough Partnership of Cooperation" will incorporate and be extended over the long haul. (Jenkins, 2018)

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